

D3.1 Proceedings from the Summer school on protein stability and folding

Name of project: Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern
Slovakia (**CasProt**)
No. 952333

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Deliverable No:	D.3.1.
Work package no. and title	Early-stage researchers: joint summer schools and training
Task no. and title:	Task 3.1.: Summer school on Protein stability and folding
Nature:	ORDP : Open Research Data Pilot
Dissemination level:	Public
Lead Beneficiary:	UPJS
Author(s):	Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, PhD.
Reviewer:	not applicable
Date of publication:	30 th of July 2022

Document History

Date	Authors	Version
30 th of July 2022	Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, PhD.	1.0

APPROVALS

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

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ABBREVIATIONS

CIB	Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences
D3.1	Deliverable 3.1 of the CasProt project
TUM	Technical University Munich
UPJS	Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice
UZH	University Zurich

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Here we describe the organization of the Summer school on protein stability and folding. The summer school was organized by UPJS and involved three Departments of two Institutes: the Department of Biophysics, the Institute of Physics, the Department of Biochemistry, Institute of Chemistry of the Faculty of sciences. The executive management and coordination of Summer school were in the hands of the Center for interdisciplinary biosciences, Technology and Innovation Park TIP-UPJS. An overall 11-day summer school on protein stability and folding consisted of several parts: the first part consisted of lectures by Slovakian and foreign researchers, which were realized during 27-28.06.2022. The second part was focused on experimental work between 29.06-4.7.2022. During this phase, the participants were split into two groups, from which one group conducted experiments at CIB, and the second group conducted experiments at the Department of Biochemistry. After two days, the groups switched locations for another two days. The third part of Summer School was devoted to hands-on theoretical training on 06.07.2022. On the last day of the summer school, all experimental results and selected publications were presented by Summer school participants. All participants had the chance to choose a research paper from protein stability and folding and present the research paper to the audience. Positive and constructive feedback was given by Assoc. Prof. Gabriel Zoldak and Assoc. prof. Rastislav Varhač. The total number of participants was 11; ten participants were able to finalize presentations and participate in experiments. Overall, six early-stage researchers were from UPJS and three students from Comenius University in Bratislava and one from scientific institutions – Slovak Academy of Sciences, Kosice. Lectures and talks were held in English. We would like to emphasize the presence of two invited speakers Dr. Abhigyan Sengupta from TU Munich, Germany, who attended the meeting in person. The second speaker, Dr.med. Magdalena Harakalova from University Utrecht, Netherland, joined the Summer School online using the WEBEX application. After the end of Summer school, a feedback questionnaire was sent to participants and data evaluation is still ongoing. We would like to emphasize that an utterly new event was established thanks to the CasProt project. We plan to organize Summer School on Protein stability and folding regularly – the next Summer school is scheduled for 2024.

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1. SUMMER SCHOOL PROGRAM

Program

Kosice
27.06 – 07.06.2022

Monday | June 27, 2022

- 09:30 – 10:00** Welcome/instructions/organization – seminar room LIDA, Jesenna 5
Chairman: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Zoldak, PhD.
- 10:00 – 10:30** **Assoc. prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlak, DrSc.** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice)
Analysis of protein thermal transitions
- 11:00 – 11:30** **Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Zoldak, PhD.** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice)
Protein stability and folding
- 12:00 – 14:00** lunch break

Chairman: RNDr. Michal Nemergut, PhD.
- 14:00 – 14:30** **Assoc. prof. RNDr. Rastislav Varhac, PhD.** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice) *Real-time monitoring of enzyme-catalysed reaction: glucose oxidase as an example*
- 15:00 – 15:30** **One-Sun Lee, PhD.** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice)
The Inhibition of Amyloid Fibril Formation of Hen Lysozyme: A Molecular Dynamics Simulation Study

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16:00 – 16:30 **RNDr. Michal Nemergut, PhD.** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice)
Role of protein aggregation in Alzheimer's disease

Tuesday | June 28, 2022

Chairman: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Rastislav Varhac, PhD.

09:00 – 09:30 **Ing. Radovan Dvorsky, PhD.** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice)
What's up with those multi-domain proteins?

10:00 – 10:30 **RNDr. Veronika Dzurillova** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice)
Protein evolution in a test tube: the case of haloalkane dehalogenases

11:00 – 11:30 **Magdalena Harakalova, MD, PhD.** (University Medical Center Utrecht)
The translational aspects of impaired protein stability and folding in genetic cardiomyopathies

12:00 – 14:00 lunch break

Chairman: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Rastislav Varhac, PhD.

14:00 – 14:30 **RNDr. Veronika Dzuptionova** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice)
Methods and techniques used for study of protein folding and stability demonstrated on pathologic human IgG light chain

15:00 – 15:30 **RNDr. Zuzana Bednarikova, PhD.** (Slovak academy of sciences)
Amyloid aggregation of proteins

16:00 – 16:30 **Abhigyan Sengupta, PhD.** (Technical University of Munich)
Ultrashort transition path time of a bacteriophage protein gpW reveals primary sequence-dependent protein (un)folding

Wednesday | June 29, 2022

09:00 – 16:00

1st group: Department of Biochemistry, Moyzesova 11, RBL foyer
Experiment: Fluorescence & Circular Dichroism
Supervisor: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Rastislav Varhac, PhD.

2nd group: Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, Trieda SNP 1, 8th floor MediPark
Experiment: Microscopy aggregates
Supervisor: RNDr. Veronika Dzubponova

Thursday | June 30, 2022

09:00 – 16:00

1st group: Department of Biochemistry, Moyzesova 11, RBL foyer
Experiment: Enzyme activity
Supervisor: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Rastislav Varhac, PhD.

2nd group: Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, Trieda SNP 1, 8th floor MediPark
Experiment: Turbidimetry, Insulin aggregation
Supervisor: RNDr. Viktoria Masatova

Friday | July 01, 2022

09:00 – 16:00

1st group: Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, Trieda SNP 1, 8th floor Medipark
Experiment: Microscopy aggregates
Supervisor: RNDr. Veronika Dzubponova

2nd group: Department of Biochemistry, Moyzesova 11, RBL foyer
Experiment: Fluorescence & Circular Dichroism
Supervisor: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Rastislav Varhac, PhD.

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Monday | July 04, 2022

09:00 – 16:00 **1st group:** Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, Trieda SNP 1, 8th floor MediPark

Experiment: Turbidimetry, Insulin aggregation

Supervisor: RNDr. Viktoria Masatova

2nd group: Department of Biochemistry, Moyzesova 11, RBL foyer

Experiment: Enzyme activity

Supervisor: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Rastislav Varhac, PhD.

Tuesday | July 05, 2022

National holiday

Wednesday | July 06, 2022

10:00 – 12:00 **1st group:** Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, Trieda SNP 1, 8th floor MediPark

Theoretical analysis using KNIME

Supervisor: RNDr. Michal Gala

12:00 – 14:00 lunch break

14:00 – 16:00 **2nd group:** Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, Trieda SNP 1, 8th floor MediPark

Theoretical analysis using KNIME

Supervisor: RNDr. Michal Gala

Thursday | July 07, 2022

09:00 – 10:30 **1st group: Jesenna 5, LIDA seminar room,**
results presentation

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10:30 – 12:00	2nd group: Jesenna 5, LIDA seminar room, results presentation
12:00 – 14:00	lunch break
14:00	End of Summer School 2022

Wishing you inspiring talks

2. SELECTED ABSTRACTS OF TALKS

Selected abstracts of Summer School lectures. Some presentations were not included because lecturers did not submit the Abstract until submission deadline 26th of July 2022.

1. Assoc. prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlak, DrSc. Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice

Analysis of protein thermal transitions

Thermal stability of proteins determines their further exploration and utilization. Therefore, the correct determination of parameters characterizing the protein thermal stability represents a critical task. There are several important properties of protein thermal transitions such as their reversibility and scan rate dependence, which determine the proper model of the transition analysis. In the talk, we discuss: (i) how to choose proper model for determination thermodynamic or kinetic thermal stability of a protein, (ii) how to derive the equation for fitting of thermal transitions, (iii) what protein stability curve expresses, and (iv) which parameter properly describe stability of protein. The talk is concluded by few remarks regarding Lumry-Eyring model describing irreversible and scan rate dependent thermal transitions and decision diagram regarding proper determination of the model of protein thermal denaturation.

2. Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, PhD. Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice

Protein stability and folding

Conformational stability, integrity, and cooperative folding of proteins are crucial to achieving a protein's functional and physiological form. Without significant conformational stability and cooperativity between the protein subdomains, the structure of the functional form of proteins would be rapidly disrupted due to thermal collisions with water molecules. The structural cooperativity of proteins is ensured by a network of interactions, formed by local and distant regions of the polypeptide chain, in a common shared space. During evolution, the complex structures of proteins were formed by the successive combination and organization of compacted regions. Such compact structures are often called protein domains. The formation of folded domains is associated with a significant restriction of the conformational space, which can be quantified employing thermodynamic parameters. The process in which the domains

are formed, the folding process, is controlled by an energy barrier, which arises as a result of the asynchronization of the compensation between the unfavorable entropic contributions and favorable enthalpy changes. Experimental biophysical methods based on chemical, thermal and/or mechanical denaturation can determine thermodynamic parameters that fully quantify the energetics of the conformational stability and the process of spontaneous protein folding.

3. Assoc. prof. RNDr. Rastislav Varhac, PhD. Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice

Real-time monitoring of enzyme-catalysed reaction: glucose oxidase as an example

There are many reasons to monitor and analyze enzyme-catalyzed reactions. Among them are cases when we want to find out basic information about the given enzyme and its substrate, such as parameters K_M , V_{max} , enzyme activity, optimal pH, or we are interested in the purity of the enzyme preparation (e.g., for comparative purposes). Also important is the use of enzymes and the need to analyze the rates of chemical reactions catalyzed by them for bioanalytical purposes. The goal of any enzyme assay is to observe time-dependent product formation or substrate loss. Using the example of the enzyme glucose oxidase (GOX, EC 1.1.3.4), the variety of possibilities for studying the reaction catalyzed by it will be shown. The results of several techniques, such as potentiometry, UV Vis spectrophotometry and fluorescence spectrophotometry, will be presented.

4. One-Sun Lee, PhD. Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice

The Inhibition of Amyloid Fibril Formation of Hen Lysozyme: A Molecular Dynamics Simulation Study

The inhibition of amyloid fibril formation using nanoparticles is a potential medicinal strategy to impede amyloid related diseases. Even though it has been reported that fullerenes have inhibition effect on amyloid formation, the mechanism of the process is not properly understood. In order to explore the inhibition mechanisms, molecular dynamics simulations of hen egg white lysozyme (HEWL), a model of amyloid-prone protein, have been performed in the presence of varied C60 concentrations to reveal how C60 affects the unfolding and amyloid fibril formation of HEWL. With the analysis of MD simulations, we found that the structural fluctuation of HEWL decreases as the concentration of C60 increases. Also, the inhibition of HEWL fibrillization by C60 is experimentally confirmed by thioflavin T fluorescence assays and atomic force microscopy.

5. RNDr. Michal Nemergut, PhD. Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice

Role of protein aggregation in Alzheimer's disease

Proteins are essential for all processes of life. To carry out their biological functions, they must adopt correct 3D structures. Protein misfolding leads to protein aggregation and accumulation of these aggregates is implicated as the main reason of neurodegenerative diseases. Here, I will discuss different factors that affect the process of protein aggregation, including thermal stability, structural plasticity, mutations, small molecules etc. The effect of these factors will be demonstrated on proteins that play a key role in the pathology of Alzheimer's disease.

6. RNDr. Veronika Dzurillova Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice

Protein evolution in a test tube: the case of haloalkane dehalogenases

The lecture provided short introduction into protein engineering approaches. Two basic approaches were presented (i) rational design and (ii) directed evolution together with their advantages and disadvantages. Application of directed evolution strategy were discussed and explained. As an example was presented the project dedicated to protein engineering of haloalkane dehalogenases by evolution-directed method ribosome display. The lecture provided also short introduction into ribosome display method and other selection techniques.

7. RNDr. Veronika Dzubonova, Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice

Methods and techniques used for study of protein folding and stability demonstrated on pathologic human IgG light chain

The stability of proteins is a key property for their proper biological function. Low protein stability leads to the formation of aggregates that are pathological for the organism and in many cases are the cause of serious diseases that affect the quality and length of life. To characterize this transformation process, it is necessary to study conformation stability (unfolding step) and colloidal stability (aggregation of unfolded protein) separately. Here, the methods to describe conformation stability at different levels of protein structure (circular dichroism, fluorescence, differential scanning calorimetry) and colloidal stability (zeta potential, dynamic light scattering, turbidimetry, mass photometry) have been demonstrated on a pathologic human IgG light chain. Finally, microscopy techniques (optical, confocal and STED microscopy) were used to analyze aggregate size and morphology using fractal scaling.

8. RNDr. Zuzana Bednarikova, PhD. Slovak academy of sciences

Amyloid aggregation of proteins

The conversion of soluble proteins into insoluble and highly stable amyloid fibrils has become the focus of attention by researchers in the last three decades. Many diseases related to amyloid formation are among the most common and debilitating disorders

of the modern era, such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease or diabetes. The amyloid-related diseases are incurable, and the effective treatments to stop their development are unsatisfactory. One of the current therapeutical strategies focuses on inhibiting and clearing amyloid fibrils using small molecules, so-called multitarget-directed ligands (MTDLs). This strategy is based on the assumption that a single compound can hit multiple targets. There are two approaches to obtaining such compounds – search the databases using in silico methods or use rational design to combine compounds with known anti-amyloid effects. In this talk, examples of both approaches will be presented. First, we have studied the mechanism of bexarotene to reduce amyloid plaques in Alzheimer's disease (AD). We have shown that a decrease of plaques is not associated with changes in the processing of the A β 42 peptide but is connected to its enhanced clearance. In silico screening of Pubchem database identified hybrid molecule CID 9998128 as a potential MTDL compound towards AD. Our in vitro study confirmed its multifunctional β -amyloid and β -secretase inhibitory effect.

9. Abhigyan Sengupta, PhD., Technical University of Munich

Ultrashort transition path time of a bacteriophage protein gpW reveals primary sequence-dependent protein (un)folding

Folding and unfolding kinetics of bacteriophage protein GpW were determined using a photon-by-photon analysis technique of the single-molecule FRET trajectories. By using a 1D and 2D free energy surface diffusion model, we extracted accurate rate coefficients and the mean transition path time in a micro-second time scale for folding and unfolding using the maximum likelihood method proposed by Gopich and Szabo. We have observed that an (α + β) secondary structural unit containing protein GpW shows a mean transition path time for (un)-folding $\sim 30 \mu\text{s}$, which is indeed a combination of α -only and β -only proteins' individual mean transition path times.

3. SUMMER SCHOOL EXPERIMENTS

EXPERIMENTAL PART - Exercise No. 1

Exercise	Potentiometric determination of the reaction rate of glucose oxidase
Supervisor:	Rastislav Varhač, Department of Biochemistry, Institute of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, UPJŠ in Košice
Annotation	The main purpose of this experiment, is to demonstrate the application of potentiometry in detecting enzyme-catalyzed reactions, specifically the one producing proton
Protocol	see Annex

EXPERIMENTAL PART - Exercise No. 2

Exercise	Spectrophotometric determination of the reaction rate of glucose oxidase
Supervisor:	Rastislav Varhač, Department of Biochemistry, Institute of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, UPJŠ in Košice
Annotation	Employment of pH indicators allows monitoring of pH changing solution as a result of enzyme-catalyzed reaction by using UV Vis spectrophotometry.
Protocol	see Annex

EXPERIMENTAL PART - Exercise No. 3

Exercise	Thermally induced conformational changes in cytochrome c
Supervisor:	Rastislav Varhač, Department of Biochemistry, Institute of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, UPJŠ in Košice
Annotation	Students will have the opportunity to observe and analyze the process of structural alteration of a simple protein. They employ two complementary instrumental techniques – fluorimetry and spectropolarimetry.
Protocol	see Annex

EXPERIMENTAL PART - Exercise No. 4

Exercise	Conformational changes of cytochrome c induced by denaturing agent
Supervisor:	Rastislav Varhač, Department of Biochemistry, Institute of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, UPJŠ in Košice

Annotation Specific chemicals that interact with a peptide bond are able to transform a fully functional protein into its dysfunctional form due to a structural change. The process of structural transformation of the protein will be monitored by fluorescence spectroscopy.

Protocol see Annex

EXPERIMENTAL PART - Exercise No. 5

Exercise Microscopy aggregates

Supervisor Veronika Džupponová, Department of Biophysics, Institute of Physics, Faculty of Science, UPJŠ in Košice

Annotation The aim of these experiments, is to compare the morphology of pathologic human IgG light chain aggregates are created by three reducing agents (DTT, GSH, and TCEP) using the fractal scaling method. In the next step the stability created by aggregates by a chemical factor (8 M urea) and mechanical factor (centrifugation) is investigated.

Protocol see Annex

EXPERIMENTAL PART - Exercise No. 6

Exercise Insulin aggregation

Supervisor Viktória Mašatová, Center for interdisciplinary biosciences UPJŠ in Košice

Annotation Insulin is a peptide hormone that aggregates when its disulfide bridges are reduced. We will examine how the presence of Hofmeister salts can control the extent of aggregation.

Protocol see Annex

THEORETICAL PART

Exercise Statistical analysis of biological data

Supervisor: Michal Gala, Department of Biophysics, Institute of Physics, Faculty of Science, UPJŠ in Košice

Annotation The course aimed to familiarize students with data mining and prediction using the so-called iris set. Next, data clustering and regression and classification were used for the dataset.

Protocol see Annex

4. SELECTED ABSTRACTS OF RELEVANT SCIENTIFIC PAPERS

The participants of the Summer school chose one of the papers below and they had to prepare a powerpoint presentation. During the last day of the Summer school, the participants presented their experimental research and one of the papers.

Žoldák G, Jancura D, Sedlák E. The fluorescence intensities ratio is not a reliable parameter for evaluation of protein unfolding transitions. Protein Sci. 2017 Jun;26(6):1236-1239. doi: 10.1002/pro.3170. Epub 2017 Apr 7. PMID: 28370732; PMCID: PMC5441425.

Abstract

Monitoring the fluorescence of proteins, particularly the fluorescence of intrinsic tryptophan residues, is a popular method often used in the analysis of unfolding transitions (induced by temperature, chemical denaturant, and pH) in proteins. The tryptophan fluorescence provides several suitable parameters, such as steady-state fluorescence intensity, apparent quantum yield, mean fluorescence lifetime, position of emission maximum that are often utilized for the observation of the conformational/unfolding transitions of proteins. In addition, the fluorescence intensities ratio at different wavelengths (usually at 330 nm and 350 nm) is becoming an increasingly popular parameter for the evaluation of thermal transitions. We show that, under certain conditions, the use of this parameter for the analysis of unfolding transitions leads to the incorrect determination of thermodynamic parameters characterizing unfolding transitions in proteins (e.g., melting temperature) and, hence, can compromise the hit identification during high-throughput drug screening campaigns.

Garajová K, Zimmermann M, Petrenčáková M, Dzurová L, Nemergut M, Škultéty I, Žoldák G, Sedlák E. The molten-globule residual structure is critical for refluination of glucose oxidase. Biophys Chem. 2017 Nov;230:74-83. doi: 10.1016/j.bpc.2017.08.009. Epub 2017 Sep 1. PMID: 28887045.

Abstract

Glucose oxidase (GOX) is a homodimeric glycoprotein with tightly bound one molecule of FAD cofactor per monomer of the protein. GOX has numerous applications, but the preparation of biotechnologically interesting GOX sensors requires a removal of the native FAD cofactor. This process often leads to unwanted irreversible defluination and, as a consequence, to the low enzyme recovery. Molecular mechanisms of reversible refluination are poorly understood; our current knowledge is based only on empiric rules, which is clearly insufficient for further development. To develop conceptual understanding of flavin-binding competent states, we studied the effect of defluination protocols on conformational properties of GOX. After defluination, the apoform assembles into soluble oligomers with nearly native-like holoform secondary structure but largely destabilized tertiary structure presumably due to the packing density defects around the vacant flavin binding site. The

reflavination is cooperative but not fully efficient; after the binding the flavin cofactor, the protein directly disassembles into native homodimers while the fraction of oligomers remains irreversibly inactivated. Importantly, the effect of Hofmeister salts on the conformational properties of GOX and reflavination efficiency indicates that the native-like residual tertiary structure in the molten-globule states favorably supports the reflavination and minimizes the inactivated oligomers. We interpret our results by combining the ligand-induced changes in quaternary structure with salt-sensitive, non-equilibrated conformational selection model. In summary, our work provides the very first steps toward molecular understanding the complexity of the GOX reflavination mechanism.

Zoldák G, Zubrik A, Musatov A, Stupák M, Sedlák E. Irreversible thermal denaturation of glucose oxidase from *Aspergillus niger* is the transition to the denatured state with residual structure. *J Biol Chem.* 2004 Nov 12;279(46):47601-9. doi: 10.1074/jbc.M406883200. Epub 2004 Aug 31. PMID: 15342626.

Abstract

Glucose oxidase (GOX; beta-d-glucose:oxygen oxidoreductase) from *Aspergillus niger* is a dimeric flavoprotein with a molecular mass of 80 kDa/monomer. Thermal denaturation of glucose oxidase has been studied by absorbance, circular dichroism spectroscopy, viscosimetry, and differential scanning calorimetry. Thermal transition of this homodimeric enzyme is irreversible and, surprisingly, independent of GOX concentration (0.2-5.1 mg/ml). It has an apparent transition temperature of 55.8 +/- 1.2 degrees C and an activation energy of approximately 280 kJ/mol, calculated from the Lumry-Eyring model. The thermally denatured state of GOX after recooling has the following characteristics. (i) It retains approximately 70% of the native secondary structure ellipticity; (ii) it has a relatively low intrinsic viscosity, 7.5 ml/g; (iii) it binds ANS; (iv) it has a low Stern-Volmer constant of tryptophan quenching; and (v) it forms defined oligomeric (dimers, trimers, tetramers) structures. It is significantly different from chemically denatured (6.67 m GdmHCl) GOX. Both the thermal and the chemical denaturation of GOX cause dissociation of the flavin cofactor; however, only the chemical denaturation is accompanied by dissociation of the homodimeric GOX into monomers. The transition temperature is independent of the protein concentration, and the properties of the thermally denatured protein indicate that thermally denatured GOX is a compact structure, a form of molten globule-like apoenzyme. GOX is thus an exceptional example of a relatively unstable mesophilic dimeric enzyme with residual structure in its thermally denatured state.

Sedlák E, Žár T, Varhač R, Musatov A, Tomášková N. Anion-Specific Effects on the Alkaline State of Cytochrome c. *Biochemistry (Mosc).* 2021 Jan;86(1):59-73. doi: 10.1134/S0006297921010065. PMID: 33705282.

Abstract

Specific effects of anions on the structure, thermal stability, and peroxidase activity of native (state III) and alkaline (state IV) cytochrome c (cyt c) have been studied by the UV-VIS absorbance spectroscopy, intrinsic tryptophan fluorescence, and circular dichroism. Thermal and isothermal denaturation monitored by the tryptophan fluorescence and circular dichroism, respectively, implied lower stability of cyt c state IV in comparison with the state III. The pKa value of alkaline isomerization of cyt c

depended on the present salts, i.e., kosmotropic anions increased and chaotropic anions decreased pKa (Hofmeister effect on protein stability). The peroxidase activity of cyt c in the state III, measured by oxidation of guaiacol, showed clear dependence on the salt position in the Hofmeister series, while cyt c in the alkaline state lacked the peroxidase activity regardless of the type of anions present in the solution. The alkaline isomerization of cyt c in the presence of 8 M urea, measured by Trp59 fluorescence, implied an existence of a high-affinity non-native ligand for the heme iron even in a partially denatured protein conformation. The conformation of the cyt c alkaline state in 8 M urea was considerably modulated by the specific effect of anions. Based on the Trp59 fluorescence quenching upon titration to alkaline pH in 8 M urea and molecular dynamics simulation, we hypothesize that the Lys79 conformer is most likely the predominant alkaline conformer of cyt c. The high affinity of the sixth ligand for the heme iron is likely a reason of the lack of peroxidase activity of cyt c in the alkaline state.

Tomášková N, Varhač R, Lysáková V, Musatov A, Sedlák E. Peroxidase activity of cytochrome c in its compact state depends on dynamics of the heme region. *Biochim Biophys Acta Proteins Proteom.* 2018 Nov;1866(11):1073-1083. doi: 10.1016/j.bbapap.2018.09.003. Epub 2018 Sep 13. PMID: 30282605.

Abstract

Cytochrome c (cyt c) is a small globular hemoprotein with the main function as an electron carrier in mitochondrial respiratory chain. Cyt c possesses also peroxidase-like activity in the native state despite its six-coordinated heme iron. In this work, we studied the effect of increasing urea concentration in the range from 0 M to 6 M at pH 7 (pH value of the bulk solvent) and pH 5 (pH value close to negatively charged membrane) on peroxidase-like activity of cyt c. We show that peroxidase-like activity, measured by guaiacol oxidation and the ferrous oxidation in xylenol orange methods, correlates with the accessibility of the heme iron, which was assessed from the association rate constant of cyanide binding to cyt c. Cyt c peroxidase-like activity linearly increases in the pre-denaturational urea concentrations (0-4 M) at both studied pHs without an apparent formation of penta-coordinated state of the heme iron. Our results suggest that dynamic equilibrium among the denaturant-induced non-native coordination states of cyt c, very likely due to reversible unfolding of the least stable foldons, is pre-requisite for enhanced peroxidase-like activity of cyt c in its compact state. Dynamic replacement of the native sixth coordination bond of methionine-80 by lysines (72, 73, and 79) and partially also by histidines (26 and 33) provides an efficient way how to increase peroxidase-like activity of cyt c without significant conformational change at physiological conditions.

Musatov A, Siposova K, Kubovcikova M, Lysakova V, Varhac R. Functional and structural evaluation of bovine heart cytochrome c oxidase incorporated into bicelles. *Biochimie.* 2016 Feb;121:21-8. doi: 10.1016/j.biochi.2015.11.018. Epub 2015 Nov 23. PMID: 26616009; PMCID: PMC4724332.

Abstract

Bilayered long- and short-chain phospholipid assemblies, known as bicelles, have been widely used as model membranes in biological studies. However, to date, there has been no demonstration of structural or functional viability for the fundamental mitochondrial electron transport complexes

reconstituted into or interacting with bicelles. In the present work, bicelles were formed from the mixture of long- and short-chain phospholipids, specifically 14:0 and 6:0 phosphatidylcholines (1,2-dimyristoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine, (DMPC) and 1,2-dihexanoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine, (DHPC)). Isolated from bovine heart, cytochrome c oxidase was successfully incorporated into bicelles. Bicelles and cytochrome c oxidase incorporated into bicelles (“proteobicelles”) were characterized by absorption spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering, atomic force microscopy, sedimentation velocity and differential scanning calorimetry. It was demonstrated that at total concentration of phospholipids $CL = 24$ mM and the molar ratio (q) of long-chain DMPC over short-chain DHPC equal to 0.4, the diameter of bicelles formed at neutral pH is in the range of 30-60 nm with the thickness of bicelles of about 4 nm. Adding cytochrome c oxidase to bicelles unified the size of the resulting proteobicelles to about 160 nm. Cytochrome c oxidase in bicelles was fully reducible by artificial donors of electrons, exhibited “normal” reaction with external ligands, and was fully active. Both, sedimentation velocity analysis and temperature-induced denaturation indicated that enzyme in bicelles is monomeric. We concluded that cytochrome c oxidase in bicelles maintains its structural and functional integrity, and that bicelles can be used for more comprehensive investigation of cytochrome c oxidase and most likely other mitochondrial electron transfer complexes.

Varhač R, Sedláková D, Stupák M, Sedlák E. Non-two-state thermal denaturation of ferricytochrome c at neutral and slightly acidic pH values. *Biophys Chem.* 2015 Aug-Sep;203-204:41-50. doi: 10.1016/j.bpc.2015.05.002. Epub 2015 May 19. PMID: 26042543.

Abstract

Thermal denaturation of ferricytochrome c (cyt c) has been methodically studied by absorbance, fluorescence, circular dichroism spectroscopy, viscosimetry and differential scanning calorimetry in pH range from pH 3.5 to 7.5. Thermal transitions have been monitored by intrinsic local probes of heme region such as absorbance at Soret, 620nm and 695nm bands and circular dichroism signals at 417nm. Global conformational changes were analyzed by circular dichroism signal at 222nm, fluorescence of the single tryptophan, reduced viscosity and differential scanning calorimetry. We show that cyt c thermal denaturation above pH ~ 5 can be described by an apparent two-step transition in which the heme iron stays in a low-spin state. The thermal denaturations of cyt c below pH ~ 5 proceed in one step to an unfolded highly compact form with a high-spin state of the heme iron. Cyt c conformational plasticity is discussed in regard to its physiological functions.

Sedlák E, Varhač R, Musatov A, Robinson NC. The kinetic stability of cytochrome C oxidase: effect of bound phospholipid and dimerization. *Biophys J.* 2014 Dec 16;107(12):2941-2949. doi: 10.1016/j.bpj.2014.10.055. PMID: 25517159; PMCID: PMC4269771.

Abstract

Thermally induced transitions of the 13-subunit integral membrane protein bovine cytochrome c oxidase (CcO) have been studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and circular dichroism (CD). Thermal denaturation of dodecyl maltoside solubilized CcO proceeds in two consecutive, irreversible, kinetically driven steps with the apparent transition temperatures at $\sim 51^\circ\text{C}$ and $\sim 61^\circ\text{C}$ (5 μM CcO at scan rate of 1.5 K/min). The thermal denaturation data were analyzed according to the Lyubarev and

Kurganov model of two consecutive irreversible steps. However, because of the limitation of the model to describe the complex mechanism of the thermal denaturation of CcO, the obtained results were utilized only for comparison purposes of kinetic stabilities of CcO under specific protein concentration (5 μ M) and scan rate (1.5 K/min). This enabled us to show that both the amphiphilic environment and the self-association state of CcO affect its kinetic stability. Kinetic stabilities of both steps are significantly decreased when all of the phospholipids are removed from CcO by phospholipase A2 (the half-life decreases at 37°C). Conversely, dimerization of CcO induced by sodium cholate significantly increases its kinetic stability of only the first step (the half-life increases at 37°C). Protein concentration-dependent nonspecific oligomerization also indicate mild stabilization of CcO. Both, reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and SDS-PAGE subunit analysis reveal that the first step of thermal denaturation involves dissociation of subunits III, VIa, VIb, and VIIa, whereas the second step is less well defined and most likely involves global unfold and aggregation of the remaining subunits. Electron transport activity of CcO decreases in a sigmoidal manner during the first transition and this dependence is very well described by kinetic parameters for the first step of the thermal transition. Therefore, dissociation of subunit III and/or VIIa is responsible for temperature-induced inactivation of CcO because VIa and VIb can be removed from CcO without affecting the enzyme activity. These results demonstrate an important role of tightly bound phospholipids and oligomeric state (particularly the dimeric form) of CcO for kinetic stability of the protein.

Varhač R. Urea-induced modification of cytochrome c flexibility as probed by cyanide binding. *Biochim Biophys Acta*. 2013 Apr;1834(4):739-44. doi: 10.1016/j.bbapap.2013.01.008. Epub 2013 Jan 19. PMID: 23337638.

Abstract

Cyanide binding to cytochrome c was monitored by absorption spectroscopy from neutral to acidic pH in the presence of urea. These results were compared with acid-induced unfolding at corresponding urea concentration monitored by absorption spectroscopy and circular dichroism. The association rate constant k_a increased 20-fold when the concentration of urea was raised from 0M to 6M at neutral pH. However, the secondary structure of the protein was not affected, i.e. there was no striking conformational change in these urea concentrations at neutral pH. At the pH that was very close to the pK of acid-induced unfolding, the k_a value reached its maximum ($k_{a,max}$) in all urea concentrations. Interestingly, the $k_{a,max}$ value increased exponentially with increasing urea concentrations. These results are interpreted in terms of a change in the flexibility of the least stable part of the cyt c structure that is responsible for the Fe-S(Met80) bond disruption and for ligand binding to heme iron.

Tomášková N, Varinská L, Sedlák E. Rate of oxidative modification of cytochrome c by hydrogen peroxide is modulated by Hofmeister anions. *Gen Physiol Biophys*. 2010 Sep;29(3):255-65. doi: 10.4149/gpb_2010_03_255. PMID: 20817949.

Abstract

Cytochrome c (cyt c) and other heme proteins are oxidatively modified in the presence of hydrogen peroxide in a concentration- and time-dependent manner. Cyt c modification has been monitored by several spectral probes by absorption spectroscopy (at wavelengths 410 nm, 530 nm), and circular dichroism (222, 268, 288 and 417 nm). Kinetics monitored with these spectral probes indicates that the oxidative modification of cyt c: i) proceeds in the order: heme --> aromatic amino acids --> secondary structure, and ii) the rate of the oxidative modification is proportional to the protein flexibility. The flexibility of cyt c was modulated by anions of Hofmeister series (sulfate, chloride, perchlorate) (Varhac et al. 2009). A minimalist scheme of the interaction of cyt c with hydrogen peroxide can be described by two steps: 1) interaction of hydrogen peroxide with heme iron forming the postulated ferryl intermediate, 2a) oxidation of another molecule of hydrogen peroxide and 2b) parallel oxidation of close amino acid residue(s) and/or heme. The catalase activity of cyt c is independent from the presence of Hofmeister anions, which indicates that both steps (1 and 2a) in the catalase reaction are independent from the flexibility of the heme region of the protein matrix. On the other hand, the flexibility of the polypeptide chain of the protein modulates the rate of parallel oxidative modification of the heme and amino acid residues.

Varhac R, Tomásková N, Fabián M, Sedlák E. Kinetics of cyanide binding as a probe of local stability/flexibility of cytochrome c. Biophys Chem. 2009 Sep;144(1-2):21-6. doi: 10.1016/j.bpc.2009.06.001. Epub 2009 Jun 6. PMID: 19545938.

Abstract

Effect of anions of the Hofmeister series (thiocyanate, perchlorate, iodide, bromide, nitrate, chloride, sulfate, and phosphate) on local and global stability and flexibility of horse heart ferricytochrome c (cyt c) has been studied. Global stability of cyt c was determined by iso/thermal denaturations monitored by change in ellipticity in the far-UV region and its local stability was determined from absorbance changes in the Soret region. Particularly, relative stability/flexibility of the Met80-heme iron bond has been assessed by analysis of binding of cyanide into the heme iron. Both global and local stabilities of cyt c exhibited monotonous increase induced by a change of anion from chaotropic to kosmotropic species. However, this monotonous dependence was not observed for the rate constants of cyanide association with cyt c. As expected more chaotropic ions induced lower stability of protein and faster binding of cyanide but this correlation was reversed for kosmotropic anions. We propose that the unusual bell-shaped dependence of the rate constant of cyanide association is a result of modulation of Met80-heme iron bond strength and/or flexibility of heme region by Hofmeister anions independently on global stability of cyt c. Further, our results demonstrate sensitivity of cyanide binding to local change in stability/flexibility in the heme region of cyt c.

Varhac R, Antalík M. Correlation of acid-induced conformational transition of ferricytochrome c with cyanide binding kinetics. J Biol Inorg Chem. 2008 Jun;13(5):713-21. doi: 10.1007/s00775-008-0357-8. Epub 2008 Mar 4. PMID: 18317818.

Abstract

A relation between pH-induced conformational transitions of horse heart ferricytochrome c and the kinetics of external ligand coordination to heme iron was investigated by optical spectroscopy, circular dichroism and viscometry. The dependencies of both the association, $k(a)$, and dissociation rate constants of cyanide binding on pH were determined from kinetic measurements. The association rate constant exhibits a bell-shaped form of dependence on pH in the region where this protein unfolds. The maximum of the dependence of $k(a)$ on pH is found to be coincident with the pK values of conformational transitions of ferricytochrome c in solutions with both low and high ionic strengths. This observation is explained in terms of ferricytochrome c unfolding, which is characterized by two processes: the gradual opening of the heme crevice accompanied by the detachment of the axial Met80 and its replacement with a water molecule. The former process enhances the rate, whereas the latter results in the inhibition of the rate of cyanide binding.

Varhac R, Antalík M, Bánó M. Effect of temperature and guanidine hydrochloride on ferrocycytochrome c at neutral pH. J Biol Inorg Chem. 2004 Jan;9(1):12-22. doi: 10.1007/s00775-003-0492-1. Epub 2003 Oct 28. PMID: 14586787.

Abstract

Optical absorption spectroscopy was used to characterize the acid-induced conformational transition of horse heart ferrocycytochrome c in the presence of urea. By using linear extrapolation to zero denaturant concentration, an apparent pK value for denaturation was found to be 0.86 ± 0.07 at 25 degrees C. Visible absorption spectra in the presence of high urea concentration indicate that the dominant population is a high-spin, five-coordinate form under acidic conditions. Ferricytochrome c, used as a model reference system, shows a linear dependence of pK values versus urea concentration in the range from 0 to 4.1 M. Our data also indicate that even at a pH below 2 the iron-sulfur bond in ferrocycytochrome c is present.

5. CONTENT OF ANNEXES

Annex consists of following items:

1. Welcome Presentation by Assoc. prof. Gabriel Zoldak
2. Protocols for Experimental Part of several authors: Assoc. prof. Rastislav Varhac, Dr. Veronika Dzuptionova, Dr. Viktoria Masatova
3. Presentation for Theoretical Part – Bioinformatics and Machine Learning by Dr. Michal Gala

asProt

Summer School on Protein Stability and Folding

Košice, 27.06-7.7.2022

Coordinator:

Cooperating partners:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

WELCOME

- 1.1 Past, Presence and Future of Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, Technology and innovation park UPJS
- 1.2 Casprot Project
- 1.3 Our Program for next days

14. 7. 2022

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

2

 CasProt

1.1 Past, Presence and Future of CIB

14. 7. 2022

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

1.2 Casprot Project

MAIN OBJECTIVES

1) Reinforcement scientific capacity and raise the research profile of the coordinating institution UPJS in the field of protein science

2) Identification and integration of the experienced and young scientists/early-stage researchers into UPJS

3) Enhance and stimulate the technological capacity of the coordinating institution UPJS

4) Strengthening the research management and administration skills at the UPJS

14. 7. 2022

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

4

1.2 Casprot Project: Specific scientific goals

1

to establish highly advanced protein evolution techniques of G-protein coupled receptors (GPCR)

2

to develop complex single-molecule assays and instrumentations for monitoring of the dynamics of wild-type and evolved GPCRs

1.3 Our Program for next days

1

Lectures 27-28.06

2

Experiments 29.06-4.07

3

National holidays 5.7.

4

Theoretical Analysis 6.7.

5

Presentations and farewell 7.7.

Tickets, Lunch, general inquiry

Contact: RNDr. Viktória Mašatová

1.3 Our Program for next days

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

Lectures 27-28.06

See PROGRAM

The image shows a poster for the CasProt Summer School program. The poster features the CasProt logo (a stylized 'C' with a protein structure) and the text 'CasProt Summer School program' in a large, bold font. Below this, it specifies the location 'Kosice' and the dates '27.06 – 07.06.2022'. The poster is divided into sections for each day of the program. The first section is for Monday, June 27, 2022, and lists three activities: a welcome/instructions/organization session from 09:30 to 10:00, a lecture by Assoc. prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlak, DrSc. from 10:00 to 10:30, and a lecture by Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Zoldak, PhD. from 11:00 to 11:30.

CasProt
Summer School
program
Kosice
27.06 – 07.06.2022

Monday | June 27, 2022

Seminar room LIDA, Jesenna 5

09:30 – 10:00 Welcome/instructions/organization

Chairman: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Zoldak, PhD.

10:00 – 10:30 **Assoc. prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlak, DrSc.** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice)
Analysis of protein thermal transitions

11:00 – 11:30 **Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Zoldak, PhD.** (Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice)
Protein stability and folding

1.3 Our Program for next days

Experiments 29.06-4.07

RNDr. Viktória Mašatová

RNDr. Veronika Džupponová

Assoc. prof. RNDr. Rastislav Varhač

See PROGRAM and MAPS
2 locations

	1st group
1	Stefana Njemoga
2	Henrieta Havalová
3	Flóra Sedlářová
4	Michaela Salaková
5	Barbora Borovská
6	Ivan Bukhun

	2nd group
1	Miroslav Kurka
2	Erik Wetter
3	Barbara Havrišová
4	Zuzana Voskárová
5	Martina Čižmáriková

1.3 Our Program for next days

Contact: RNDr. Viktória Mašatová

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

National holidays 5.7.

1.3 Our Program for next days

Theoretical Analysis 6.7.

RNDr. Michal Gala

All groups

	1st group
1	Stefana Njemoga
2	Henrieta Havalová
3	Flóra Sedlářová
4	Michaela Salaková
5	Barbora Borovská
6	Ivan Bukhun

	2nd group
1	Miroslav Kurka
2	Erik Wetter
3	Barbara Havriřová
4	Zuzana Voskárová
5	Martina Čiřmáriková

1.3 Our Program for next days

1

2

3

4

5

1. Each participant presents 1 paper in 10 minutes
2. Leaders of group 1 and 2 present experimental results
 - IMPORTANT: please send all your presentations till 6th of July

Presentations and farewell 7.7.

Thank you!

Organization:

RNDr. Viktória Mašatová

14. 7. 2022

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

Any questions?

Potentiometric determination of the reaction rate of glucose oxidase

Introduction

Glucose oxidase (GOX, EC 1.1.3.4) is a homodimeric protein that catalyzes oxidation of glucose to glucono- δ -lactone according to the following scheme:

Gluconolactone is relatively unstable and spontaneously hydrolyzes to gluconic acid that further dissociates to its anion and a proton:

The latter can be very efficiently detected by a combined glass pH electrode. We have used this approach to monitor the progress of glucose oxidation by GOX. The reaction ran in a plastic tube immersed in a beaker filled with water. The connection of the pH meter with the PC enables the collection of data (pH values depending on time) at specified intervals, which we can further analyze.

Materials and chemicals

GOX solution	magnetic stirrer
NaCl solution	thermometer
glucose solution	micropipettes
distilled water	glass syringe
calibration solutions (pH 7.0 and 4.0)	plastic tube
glass pH electrode	mini water bath
pH meter	PC, software, data cable

Procedure

1. Pipette distilled water, NaCl, GOX into a plastic tube.
2. All mix well with a magnetic stirrer.
3. Wait a few minutes for the temperature of the solution to stabilize.
4. Add glucose solution, mix and start data collection (10 minutes).
5. In this way, we perform a series of five measurements, each with a different concentration of GOX:

Measurement #	1	2	3	4	5	Final concentration
distilled H_2O (μ l)	9843	9837	9823	9810	9797	–
2 M NaCl (μ l)	100	100	100	100	100	20 mM
37.4 μ M GOX (μ l)	6.7	13.4	26.7	40	53	0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2 μ M
1 M glucose (μ l)	50	50	50	50	50	5 mM

Analysis

The first, more simple way to analyse the results is to calculate the proportion of $|\Delta pH|/\Delta t$ in the initial stages of the reaction (linear part of the curve). This gives the absolute value of the pH change at time t . The second method is a bit more complicated. The first step is a conversion of the pH values to

corresponding $[H^+]$. Dependence of $[H^+]$ versus time is fitted by a polynomial equation. Finally, from the first derivative of this polynomial fit, we calculate the reaction rate as the change in $[H^+]$ over time for a given pH value.

Conclusion

We state the effect of increasing enzyme concentration (GOX) on the reaction rate under given conditions (temperature, ionic strength, substrate concentration) and we compare the results with another, independent method (in our case UV Vis spectrophotometry in the presence of a pH indicator, exercise 2).

References

1. Varhač R., Schneiderová N., *Potentiometry as a tool to study enzyme kinetics*, 8th Slovak Biophysical Symposium, May 30 – June 1, 2018, Košice, Slovakia, Book of Contributions (reviewed), p. 83 – 84, poster PO22.
2. Dankovčíková K., Gančár M., Varhač R., *Application of potentiometry in a study of enzymatic reactions: Glucose oxidase as an example*, 11th International Conference: Structure and Stability of Biomacromolecules SSB 2019, September 3 – 6, 2019, Košice, Slovakia, Book of Abstracts (reviewed), p. 117 – 118, poster PO26.

Spectrophotometric determination of the reaction rate of glucose oxidase

Introduction

The oxidation rate of glucose catalyzed by the GOX can also be monitored visually through the color change of the solution in the presence of a suitable pH indicator. Examples of color changes of selected pH indicators in the pH range 7.0 to 3.5 are shown in the following figure:

MR = methyl red, BTB = bromothymol blue, BCP = bromocresol purple,
PR = phenol red, BCG = bromocresol green

In the case of GOX-catalyzed conversion of glucose to gluconolactone and its subsequent spontaneous hydrolysis to gluconic acid, the pH varies in the range from 6 to 4. Therefore, MR and BCG appear to be the most suitable of the above pH indicators. By measuring the absorbance change in time of a solution containing a pH indicator, we can, similarly to the potentiometric method, determine the rate of the respective reaction. However, since there is no direct relationship between the absorbance of the indicator and the pH value, it is necessary to construct a calibration curve which represents the dependence of the absorbance at a certain wavelength on pH. A suitable wavelength is characterized by maximum changes in absorbance that occur within a certain range of pH values. The figure below shows examples of spectral changes (left) and calibration curves (right) for MR (part A) and BCG (part B):

Materials and chemicals

GOX solution	pH meter
NaCl solution	thermometer
glucose solution	micropipettes
distilled water	glass syringe
HCl and NaOH solutions for pH adjustment	two 3.5-ml plastic cuvettes (macrocuvettes)
calibration solutions (pH 7.0 and 4.0)	pH indicators (MR, BCG)
glass pH electrode	UV Vis spectrophotometer

Procedure

1. Pipette distilled water, NaCl, GOX, pH indicator (MR or BCG) into a plastic cuvette.
2. Mix well.
3. Place the cuvette in the cuvette holder and wait a few minutes for the temperature of the solution to stabilize.
4. Set the kinetic mode on the spectrophotometer (524 nm for MR, or 614 nm for BCG).
5. Add glucose solution, mix and start the measurement (10 minutes).
6. In this way, we perform a series of five measurements, each with a different concentration of GOX:

Measurement #	1	2	3	4	5	Final concentration
distilled H ₂ O (μl)	2457/2451	2456/2450	2452/2446	2449/2443	2446/2440	–
2 M NaCl (μl)	25	25	25	25	25	20 mM
37.4 μM GOX (μl)	1.7	3.3	6.7	10	13.4	0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2 μM
18.6 mM MR/7.2 mM BCG (μl)	3.6/9.4	3.6/9.4	3.6/9.4	3.6/9.4	3.6/9.4	27 μM
1 M glucose (μl)	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	5 mM

Construction of the calibration curve:

1. In scanning mode of the spectrophotometer, set the range of wavelengths to 450 - 650 nm for MR, or 470 - 670 nm for BCG.
2. In the range of pH 7 to 3.5, measure the absorption spectra (each for a corresponding pH value, 12 to 15 spectra totally) of the pH indicator (MR or BCG).
3. Adjust the pH value of the indicator solution with either HCl or NaOH as needed.
4. The pH measurement is performed after each adjustment by immersing the glass pH electrode in the indicator solution.

Analysis

After the completion of the whole series (12 to 15 spectra) construct a dependence of the measured absorbance at 524 nm (MR), or at 614 nm (BCG), on pH. Fit the points using an equation for the so-called S-curve. This curve will be used to convert the absorbance values obtained from the glucose oxidation rate measurements to pH values. The further procedure is identical with **exercise 1**.

Conclusion

State the effect of increasing enzyme concentration (GOX) on the reaction rate under given conditions (temperature, ionic strength, substrate concentration, presence of pH indicator) and compare the results with another, independent method (in our case potentiometry, **exercise 1**).

References

1. Dankovčíková K., *Využitie potenciometrie pri štúdiu enzýmovej kinetiky*, diploma thesis, PF UPJŠ v Košiciach, 2020.

Thermally induced conformational changes in cytochrome c

Introduction

In addition to covalent bonds (peptide bonds), which link amino acids to the polypeptide chain, non-covalent interactions (hydrogen bonds, Van der Waals interactions, ionic bonds, hydrophobic interactions) are also important for proteins. Thanks to those interactions, proteins acquire their unique spatial structures, which allows them to perform their natural functions in organisms. Less or more extensive disruption of these interactions will usually cause a partial or complete change in the protein structure. *In vivo*, subtle changes in the structure are often necessary to regulate a variety of processes, or metabolic pathways. The process that leads to the transformation of the structure from native (natural) to non-native, is known as denaturation. It usually results in a complete loss of protein function. All these changes in protein structure are generally referred to as conformational changes. In a laboratory, we can induce changes in the structure of the protein by means of physical (temperature, pressure) or chemical (pH change, presence of various specific substances such as denaturing agents, detergents) factors. Depending on the extent of the relevant factor and the "resistance" (stability) of the protein, smaller or larger conformational changes can be induced. One of the most applied factors for inducing conformational changes and studying the stability of proteins is temperature. The supply of heat increases the kinetic energy, and thus the mobility of individual atoms in the macromolecule. This leads to the interruption of stabilizing interactions. It is generally known that the structure of proteins is hierarchical (primary, secondary, tertiary, quaternary). Accordingly, there are instrumental techniques that make it possible to monitor conformational changes at various levels of protein structure. A unique technique that monitors changes at the secondary structure level is spectropolarimetry (circular dichroism, CD). In the case of the tertiary structure changes, it is possible to use e.g. UV Vis absorption or fluorescence spectrophotometry. A specific feature of cytochrome c is a presence of a single tryptophan (Trp) in its primary structure. And a fluorescence of that tryptophan was found to be dependent on its distance from the heme group in cytochrome c.

Materials and chemicals

cytochrome c solution	micropipettes
buffer solutions with pH 7 and 3	vortex
two 1.4-ml quartz cuvettes for fluorescence measurements	fluorescence spectrophotometer
1-mm quartz cuvette for ellipticity measurements	spectropolarimeter
1.5-ml plastic microtubes with a lid	

Procedure

For fluorescence or ellipticity measurement, we use cuvettes specifically designed for the corresponding instrument. The solutions are added into the cuvette according to the following table:

	fluorescence measurement ^a	CD measurement ^b
buffer solution (μl)	997	296
4 mM cytochrome c (μl)	3	4
cyt c concentration in a cuvette (μM)	12	53

^a A sample is prepared directly in a 1.4-ml semi-microcuvette.
^b A 1.5-ml plastic microtube with a lid is used to prepare a sample.

Start the measurement after inserting the sample containing cuvette into a cuvette holder of the corresponding instrument and setting the parameters.

Analysis

Using the acquired data, construct a dependence of the observed signal (fluorescence, ellipticity) at a given wavelength on temperature. Fit these temperature dependences by the equation of the S-curve and calculate the value of T_{trs} (transition temperature) at a given pH.

Conclusion

Compare the cytochrome *c* transition temperatures found at two different pH values and by two different techniques. Try to explain what kind of a process caused the observed changes.

References

1. Varhač R., Sedláková D., Stupák M., Sedlák E. (2015). Non-two-state thermal denaturation of ferricytochrome *c* at neutral and slightly acidic pH values. *Biophys. Chem.*, 203-204, pp. 41-50.

Conformational changes of cytochrome c induced by denaturing agent

Introduction

In addition to temperature, a denaturing agent can be used to achieve conformational changes in proteins, with the temperature remaining constant during the measurement. The most commonly used denaturing agents in protein chemistry are urea and guanidinium hydrochloride. Cytochrome c contains a non-proteinaceous component in its structure, a heme which is attached to the polypeptide chain by two covalent bonds. In addition, the iron ion, which is located in the center of the heme group, is attached to the polypeptide chain by two coordination covalent bonds provided on the one side by histidine at position 18 (His18) and on the other side by methionine at position 80 (Met80). The action of the denaturant results in destabilization of the cytochrome c structure, which leads to the replacement of Met80 by another amino acid. The accompanying phenomenon is, similarly to the temperature-induced conformational change, an increase in the distance between the heme and tryptophan at position 59 (Trp59), which can be monitored by fluorescence spectroscopy.

Spatial structure of cytochrome c (PDB ID: 1HRC). The central iron ion is dark blue, His18 (right of iron) and Met80 (left of iron) are marked in light blue. The heme is light green.

Structure of heme c.

Materials and chemicals

cytochrome c solution
buffer solutions with pH 6 and 3
0.7-ml quartz cuvette for fluorescence measurements
1.5-ml and 5-ml plastic microtubes with a lid

micropipettes
vortex
glass syringe
fluorescence spectrophotometer

Procedure

1. First, prepare a series of solutions with different urea concentrations according to the table.

- Pipette the solutions into prepared and numbered 1.5-ml plastic microtubes.
- Mix them well.
- Add 10 μl of cytochrome *c* stock solution (0.5 mM) to each 1.5-ml microtube before measurement and mix. Its final concentration in the microtube is therefore 12.5 μM .
- To measure the fluorescence, use a 0.7-ml microcuvette. Pipette the solution from the first 1.5-ml tube into the microcuvette. Measure the fluorescence spectrum and then replace it by the next solution in order.
- Follow this procedure until the last prepared solution.

Measurement #	Buffer solution (μl)	Buffer solution + 8 M urea (μl)	Final urea concentration ^a (M)
1	400	0	0
2	350	50	0.98
3	300	100	1.95
4	250	150	2.93
5	220	180	3.51
6	190	210	4.10
7	160	240	4.68
8	130	270	5.27
9	100	300	5.85
10	70	330	6.44
11	40	360	7.02
12	20	380	7.41
13	0	400	7.80

^a The volume of cytochrome *c* (10 μl) is also included in the calculation.

Analysis

Using the acquired data, construct a dependence of the observed signal fluorescence emission at a given wavelength on urea concentration. Fit this dependence by the equation of the S-curve and calculate the value of ΔG (change in Gibbs energy for the transition from the native to the non-native state of the protein) at a given temperature and pH.

Conclusion

Compare the cytochrome *c* ΔG and C_m (the concentration of urea required to denature half of the population of protein molecules) values found at two different pH values (each of the two groups will perform the measurement at a different pH value). Try to explain what kind of a process caused the observed changes.

References

- Bushnell G., Louie G., Brayer G. (1990). High-resolution 3-dimensional structure of horse heart cytochrome *c*. *J. Mol. Biol.*, 214, pp. 585-595.

INTRODUCTION

Amyloidosis of IgG light chain

Light chain is part of IgG which consists of variable (V-domain) and constant domain (C-domain). The structure of both domains is composed of ca. 9 β – strands, which are assembled into compact typical immunoglobulin fold structure and covalently linked by a disulfide bond. While sequence of C-domains is highly conserved, V-domains contain at certain positions hypervariable sequences, so-called CDRs (acronym of Complementarity Determining Regions). Because of their large sequence variability in CDRs, V- domains can have an increased tendency to form amyloid fibrils and aggregates. If light chain expression is dysregulated, high aggregation propensity of V-domains can lead to severe pathologies such as amyloidosis and multiple myeloma.

Multiple myeloma (MM) is the second most common haematological malignancy, manifested by uncontrolled proliferation and accumulation of damaged plasma cells in the bone marrow. As a result of genetic dysregulation of heavy chain of immunoglobulin G (IgG) production, myelomatic plasma cells produce in very high concentration of light chain of IgG (LC) which is subsequently secreted into the bloodstream. From the blood circulation, LC is gradually captured in organs important for life, such as heart, kidney and liver, where due to the low colloidal stability of the LC it forms aggregates and at the final stage it forms the microscopic fibrils or amyloid deposits (for amyloidosis).

Understanding the molecular nature of protein aggregation and the effect of the physicochemical environment that accelerates the conversion of functional forms of proteins into pathogenic aggregates is a key to discovering the reasons for the high morbidity of these leukemic diseases and consequently the rational development of drugs that inhibit the formation of toxic aggregates.

Fractal scaling

Besides the measurements of the aggregate size and of the aggregate content, it is relevant to characterize the aggregate morphology, which can be investigated with microscopy techniques. Depending on the solution conditions and on the environmental stress, a given protein can form aggregates of various morphologies. The concept of fractal scaling relies on the assumption of a scale invariant geometry, also called self-similarity. Namely, it unifies various irregular aggregate morphologies that would be otherwise difficult to rationalize, by relating the aggregate mass with aggregate size according to:

$$i = k_f \times \left(\frac{R_i}{R_p}\right)^{d_f}$$

where d_f is the fractal dimension, k_f is the scaling prefactor usually in the order of unity, R_p is the radius of a primary particle, and R_i is the radius of an aggregate containing i primary particles.

It is nevertheless worth mentioning that the notion of fractal scaling theoretically refers to scale invariance over infinite dimensions, while in this context it is used in an effective manner over the aggregate discrete sizes, ranging from the monomer to the largest aggregate formed in the system.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Preparation of aggregates

Sample of human light chain aggregates is prepared by reduction with 2 mM reducing agents (DTT; TCEP; GSH) at 50 °C. To aliquot of stock protein solution (volume 12 µl, concentration 1 mg/ml) add 15 µl of buffer PBS (10 mM, pH 7.4) and 3 µl of reducing agent – DTT (dithiothreitol); TCEP (tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine); or GSH (glutathione) from stock solutions (20 mM), mix the solution and put it at thermoblock at 50 °C for 30 minutes. Final concentration of protein in sample is 0.4 mg/ml and final concentration of reducing agent is 2 mM.

Effect of different reducing agents on aggregate morphology

Analyze of prepared samples by optical light microscope Konus with objective 40x and visualize with CMOS camera Kern ODC 825 (5.1 MP), analyze images by ImageJ-FIJI software (National Institutes of Health, USA) – described below, and compare morphology of aggregates prepared by reduction with different reducing agents.

Effect of mechanical forces on the stability of prepared aggregates

Prepare samples with aggregates, how was described above. Centrifuge samples at 20 000 g and analyze by optical light microscope and ImageJ-FIJI software. Compare morphology of aggregates before centrifugation and after applied mechanical forces.

Effect of chemical factor on the stability of prepared aggregates

Prepare samples with aggregates, how was described above. Add 4 µl of 8 M urea to prepared samples (final concentration of urea in the sample is 1 M), and heat of aggregate samples at 50 °C for 30 minutes. Analyze by optical light microscope and ImageJ-FIJI software. Compare morphology of aggregates without and with denaturing agent urea.

IMAGE ANALYSIS

Image processing – ImageJ-FIJI

Background creation: Open image (File→Open) → Create 8-bit image (Image→Type→8-bit) → Create background (Process→Subtract background) *set parameters: rolling ball radius 50 pixels; light background; create background (don't subtract)

Background subtraction: Open same image → Create 8-bit image → Subtract background (Process→Image calculator) *subtract background (1st image) from image (2nd image), set parameters: create new window; 32-bit (float) result

Threshold image: Create 8-bit image from new image with subtracted background → Set Threshold – red color must fill the individual particles of aggregate (Image→Adjust→Threshold)

Analyzing of particles: Image with set Threshold (Analyze→Analyze Particles) * set parameters: Size (pixel²): 82-Infinity; Show: Outlines; Display results; Clear results; Add to manager; Exclude on edges

Result: Table with data (R_p, i) for analyzed aggregate *area is in unit pixel² it is required change to µm² (multiplying by 0.01 µm², this value was obtained from calibration of microscope – 1 pixel = 0.1 µm)

Analyzing of aggregate area: chose the circle function and line the silhouette of aggregate → Analyze (Measure) → Calculate value R_i from obtained Area of aggregate in correct unit.

Formula for calculation is:
$$R_i = \sqrt{\frac{\overline{area}}{\pi}}$$

Analyzing by fractal scaling

From obtained values calculate fractal dimension d_f according to the following equation:

$$d_f = \frac{\ln \left(\frac{k_i}{k_j} \right)}{\ln \left(\frac{R_j}{R_i} \right)}$$

R_p

Compare the values i , R_i , R_p , and d_r of aggregates prepared by different reducing agents; and aggregates destabilized by mechanical forces and chemical factor – urea.

Insulin is a peptide hormone produced by β cell of the pancreatic islets, active insulin consists of two chains (A & B) linked by disulfide bonds. It plays an important role in the human body by regulating glucose levels. But improper storage and influence of unwanted factors, such as temperature or pH, can cause formation of insoluble aggregates or amyloid fibrils.

Fig.1: Insulin structure

Amyloid fibrils are formed by normally soluble proteins, which assemble to form insoluble fibers that are resistant to degradation. Their formation can accompany disease and each disease is characterized by a specific protein or peptide that aggregates. Well known examples of amyloid diseases include Alzheimer's disease, Diabetes type II and the spongiform encephalopathies. The amyloid fibrils are deposited extracellularly in the tissues and are thought to have a pathogenic effect. The fibrillar assemblies are inherently stable and structural studies have revealed that they are composed predominantly of β -sheet structure in a characteristic cross- β conformation. Amyloid fibrillation can be described as sigmoidal

curve, divided into three parts:

1. lag-phase: protein unfolding due environment, nuclei formation from monomers
2. elongation phase/growth phase: exponential growth, adding monomers to nuclei (rich in β -sheet structures), transformation from nuclei to fibrils
3. plateau phase: mature fibrils

Fig.2: Amyloid aggregation

Application of various organic and inorganic additives can successfully stabilize the insulin structure and prevent the formation of amyloid fibrils. Such a inhibitors can be anions of the Hofmeister ion series. Depending on the properties, these anions can be divided into two groups, chaotropic and kosmotropic ions, which can affect protein stability, surface tension or denaturation.

Fig.3: Hofmeister series

Concentration dependence & influence of two Hofmeister anions on insulin aggregation using reducing agent

1. Prepare 200 μ M (1,16 mg/ml; molarity(M) = concentration(c) / molar mass (MW)) insulin stock solution in 200 μ l dH₂O, to enhance solubility add few drops of HCl (pH = 2,0), then add 10X PBS and 2X PBS to make pH of solution neutral (pH = 7,4) – final concentration and volume: 200 μ M in 1 ml at pH = 7,4
2. Mix the solution well
3. Check the absorbance (at 280 nm) of the stock solution using NanoPhotometer and determine molarity again (using Lambert-Beer law; $\epsilon_{\text{INS}} = 6335 \text{ M}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$; $\text{MW}_{\text{INS}} = 5807 \text{ Da}$)

Concentration dependence:

1. Dilute stock solution - 3 different concentrations using 1X PBS (100 μ M; 45 μ M and 20 μ M (each concentration will be repeated 3 times)
2. Pipette prepared volumes in the microplate

INS concentration	Volume of INS stock solution*	Volume of 1X PBS*	Volume of (TCEP)	Final volume
100 μM	55 μ l	45 μ l	10 μ l	110 μ l
45 μM	24,75 μ l	72,25 μ l	10 μ l	110 μ l
20 μM	11 μ l	89 μ l	10 μ l	110 μ l

* If the molarity is 200 μ M; volume depends on final concentration of the stock solution; using dilution equation ($c_1 \cdot V_1 = c_2 \cdot V_2$)

3. Add reducing agent before starting a kinetic experiment
4. Start experiment for 30 minutes at 50°C (temperature will speed up the experiment)

Influence of Hofmeister anion series:

1. Dilute stock solution – only 45 μ M using 1X PBS (3 times for each salt concentration)
2. Pipette prepared volumes in the microplate

Salt concentration	Volume of salt solution	Volume of INS stock solution*	Volume of 1X PBS*	Volume of (TCEP)	Final volume
1,00 M	55 μ l	24,75 μ l	20,25 μ l	10 μ l	110 μ l
0,5 M	27,5 μ l	24,75 μ l	47,75 μ l	10 μ l	110 μ l
0,25 M	13,75 μ l	24,75 μ l	61,5 μ l	10 μ l	110 μ l

* If the molarity is 200 μ M; volume depends on final concentration of the stock solution; using dilution equation ($c_1 \cdot V_1 = c_2 \cdot V_2$)

3. Add reducing agent before starting a kinetic experiment
4. Start experiment for 30 minutes at 50°C (temperature will speed up the experiment)

After experiments - make time dependence graph based on absorbance at 340 nm using Microsoft Excel or Igor 7.0/8.0

Bioinformatics and machine learning

 CasProt

RNDr. Michal Gala

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TIP
UPJŠ

- 1. Bioinformatics and machine learning overview – Presentation**
- 2. Iris data analysis in KNIME – Hands on training**
 - How to do fast statistical analysis of experimental data
 - How to make prediction model (regression and classification)
- 3. Bioinformatics in department of biophysics and CIB – Presentation**

Bioinformatics and computational biology

What is bioinformatics?

- Bioinformatics and computational biology are interdisciplinary research areas at the interface between biological and computational sciences

According to NIH:

- **Bioinformatics:** Research, development, or application of computational tools and approaches for expanding the use of biological, medical or health data, including organize, archive, analyze, or visualize data.
- **Computational Biology:** The development and application of data-analytical and theoretical methods, mathematical modeling and computational simulation techniques to the study of biological and social systems.

History and origin of bioinformatics

- The term bioinformatics was first introduced in 1970 by Hogeweg and Hesper
- But bioinformatics comes with the development of methods for protein sequencing after Frederick Sanger was able to determine the sequence of insulin in the early 1950s.
- It was necessary to develop new computer methods for the analysis of a large number of protein sequences.
- Dayhoff's collaboration with physicist Robert S. Ledley between 1958 and 1962 led to the development of the "COMPROTEIN" program.
- It was a computer program used to determine the primary structure of proteins using peptide sequencing data. It was the first program that could assemble small fragments of a sequence into large one.

Few examples of bioinformatics applications

- 1. Building and management of biological databases**
- 2. Morbidity and pathogenicity based on sequence analysis**
- 3. Evolution analysis**
- 4. Analysis of 3D protein structures**

Building and management of biological databases

Sequencing is cheaper and more affordable. The number of sequences in biological databases is growing very fast

J. Gaffney et al.

Global Food Security 26 (2020) 100411

1. Logical database architecture. The user can effectively find and use this information.
2. Data curation and updating of information.

Morbidity and pathogenicity based on sequence analysis

Comparison of sequences can find the origin of a disease at the molecular level

Raw sequences

1. ZDRAVY	A	T	G	G	C	A	A	A	T	T	G	C	M	A	N	C
2. CHORY	A	T	G	G	C	A	T	G	C	M	A	C				
3. ZDRAVY_2	A	T	G	G	C	A	A	A	T	T	G	C	M	A	N	C
4. ZDRAVY_3	A	T	G	G	C	A	A	A	T	T	G	C	M	A	N	C
5. ZDR_ALEBO_CHR	A	T	G	G	G	A	A	G	T	T	G	C	M	G	S	C

Sequences after alignment

1. ZDRAVY	A	T	G	G	C	A	A	A	T	T	G	C	M	A	N	C
2. CHORY	A	T	G	G	C	A	-	-	-	T	G	C	M	A	-	C
3. ZDRAVY_2	A	T	G	G	C	A	A	A	T	T	G	C	M	A	N	C
4. ZDRAVY_3	A	T	G	G	C	A	A	A	T	T	G	C	M	A	N	C
5. ZDR_ALEBO_CHR	A	T	G	G	G	A	A	G	T	T	G	C	M	G	S	C

SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein, Poland

26. QLJ53560.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
27. QLJ53572.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
28. QLJ53584.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
29. QLJ53596.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
30. QLJ53608.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	S	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
31. QLJ53620.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
32. QOL21539.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
33. QOL21723.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
34. QPF48056.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
35. QPF48068.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	-	-	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
36. QPF48080.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
37. QPF48092.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
38. QPF48104.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
39. QPF48116.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	L	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
40. QPF48128.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
41. QPF48140.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
42. QPF48152.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
43. QPF48164.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
44. QPF48176.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
45. QPF48188.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G
46. QPF48200.1_surfacD	L	E	G	K	Q	G	N	F	K	N	L	R	E	F	V	F	K	N	I	D	G	Y	F	K	I	Y	S	K	H	T	P	I	N	L	V	R	D	L	P	Q	G	F	S	A	L	E	P	L	V	D	L	P	I	G	I	N	I	T	R	F	Q	T	L	L	A	L	H	R	S	Y	L	T	P	G	D	S	S	S	G	W	T	A	G

Phylogenetic analysis

The most common result of phylogenetic analysis is phylogenetic tree

Phylogenetic analysis is the study of the evolution of a species, group of organisms or a specific property of an organism

Why is phylogenetic research important?

1. Describes relationships between organisms (e.g. parent-child).
2. Help with taxonomy classification.
3. Describes the origin of pathogens (SARS-CoV-2) = health policy recommendations.
4. Plant protection policy = difficult decisions which species to try to prevent against extinction.

doi:10.1126/science.aad4597

LI, Tingting, et al. Phylogenetic supertree reveals detailed evolution of SARS-CoV-2. Scientific reports, 2020, 10.1: 1-9.

3D structure protein analysis

How structural features shape host pathogen interaction or pathogen evolution?

- Spike protein
- ACE2 receptor
- Receptor binding domain
- Omicron mutácie

PDB: 6XLU

PDB: 7A94

15/36 mutations

Machine learning and protein biophysics

What is machine learning?

Machine learning

is a subfield of artificial intelligence which include methods and algorithms that allow a program to learn and then respond to various inputs without being explicitly programmed for them, based only on the information that they learned.

3 common tasks

- Clustering
- Classification
- Regression

Based on learning:

- Unsupervised Learning = user provide only data, not other information
- Supervised Learning = data are for example categorized
- Reinforcement Learning

nature **AlphaFold2**

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NEWS · 30 NOVEMBER 2020

'It will change everything': DeepMind's AI makes gigantic leap in solving protein structures

Google's deep-learning program for determining the 3D shapes of proteins stands to transform biology, say scientists.

DeepMind > Blog > AlphaFold: a solution to a 50-year-old grand challenge in biology

10 NOV 2020

AlphaFold: a solution to a 50-year-old grand challenge in biology

Workflow of prediction model

Regression a classification

Regression - Linear regression

$$y = ax + b$$

- y is dependent variable
- x is an independent variable
- a is the slope of the regression line
- b indicates the coordinates of the beginning of the regression line

Classification – Support Vector Machine

- As linear method
- The separating hyperplane divides the space by trying to have the greatest possible distance from the nearest points of different classes = the Margin tries to be as wide as possible.

Kernel Trick

KNIME analytics platform

KNIME analytics platform

- KNIME is a free and open-source data analytics, reporting and integration platform.
- KNIME integrates various components for machine learning and data mining through its modular data pipelining "Building Blocks of Analytics" concept.
- It has graphical user interface and allows assembly of nodes blending different data sources, including preprocessing, for modeling, data analysis and visualization without, or with only minimal, programming.

Iris dataset

Description of Iris dataset

The Iris data set contains measurements in cm for the features:

1. Sepal length
2. Sepal Width
3. Petal length
4. Petal width

for 150 flowers from 3 iris species:

1. Iris Setosa,
2. Iris Versicolor
3. Iris Virginica.

The data was collected over several years by Edgar Anderson, who used the data to show that the measurements could be used to differentiate between different species of irises.

Iris Versicolor

Iris Setosa

Iris Virginica